

File Edit View Help
Align CP1: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091

← → *Mus musculus* mRNA for testin2, X78990.1 Predict Primer Design Save

58.6% in a region of 256 nt

Selected 256 bases from base 395 to 650 (256 ungapped bases from base 395 to 650).

4 new notifications

File Edit View Settings Help
Align CP1: MtrunA17_Chr0c01g0489091, altORF2

← → *Mus musculus* testin2, X78990.1 Editing Annotate & Predict Save

32.9% in a region of 70 aa

File Edit View Help
Align CP114: MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401 info

Homo sapiens Humanin (HN1) mRNA, complete cds, AY029066.1

67.4% in a region of 196 nt

Consensus
Identity
1. AY029066.1
2. MtrunA17_Chr7g0229401 cDNA

File Edit View Help
Align CP89: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291 Info

Candida albicans SC5314 Tar1p (TAR1), partial mRNA, XM_019475565.1
73.3% in a region of 285 nt

CP87: MtrunA17_Chr5g0421761

Reticulitermes flavipes rRNA-like mRNA, partial sequence, AY572860.1

80.5% in a region of 41 nt

File Edit View Help
Align CP88: MtrunA17_Chr5g0422291 Info

Reticulitermes flavipes rRNA-like mRNA, partial sequence, AY572860.1
88.3% in a region of 417 nt

Supplementary Dataset S31. Alignments of four PRF-related rRNA transcripts with known rRNA-like mRNA transcripts. Percent identity values are based on Geneious® alignments (Geneious® v. 7.1, Dotmatics Ltd., MA, USA, <https://www.geneious.com>). Codes at the end of the annotated gene names are GenBank identifiers. Alternative ORFs (altORFs) are shown in pink. Numbers 1 and 2 on altORFs indicate the following. An altORF1 in this study is defined as the one that starts earlier than an altORF2. Switches from altORF2 to altORF1 are also found in this dataset but are five times less frequent (e.g. CP108 and four other CPs). Positions and the direction of programmed ribosomal frameshifting (PRF) events are labeled with deep purple arrowheads.